

MEDICAL SCIENCES

TREATMENT OF PERIODONTAL DISEASES THROUGH DIRECT PROSTHETICS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8383648>

Abstract

Treatment of periodontal diseases remains quite a complex task and can only be effective with an integrated approach that includes therapeutic, surgical and orthopedic treatment. . It is extremely important to eliminate the functional traumatic overload of the periodontium through selective grinding, splinting and rational prosthetics. Orthopedic treatment of periodontal diseases can reduce the number of manifestations of inflammatory phenomena, eliminate pathological mobility of teeth, normalize occlusion, and redistribute chewing pressure.

Keywords: Periodontal diseases, tooth mobility, immediate dentures.

Goal: increasing the effectiveness of treatment of periodontal diseases. Patients and methods. The first group included 24 patients who had teeth removed due to chronic generalized periodontitis. Patients in this group refused to manufacture immediate prostheses. All patients had removable orthopedic structures installed in the long term after tooth extraction (from 4 months to one year). The second group consisted of 24 people with severe forms of periodontal disease who required tooth extraction. On the day of tooth extraction, removable immediate dentures were applied to the surface of the jaw wound. The condition of the periodontal tissues of the teeth, limiting the dentition defect, was assessed and X-ray studies were carried out. To assess the mineral density of bone tissue in the area of extracted teeth, echo-osteometry was performed before tooth extraction, as well as after 12 months. Results. The application of an immediate prosthesis to the surface of the wound contributes not only to the formation of the alveolar process, but also to the restoration of mineral density in the area. and high-quality fixation of orthopedic structures.

A correctly selected and applied set of orthopedic interventions, aimed not only at restoring dental defects, but also at reliable stabilization of remaining teeth, helps to normalize occlusal relationships, periodontal trophism and reparative processes in its tissues. 2, 3]. However, often the removal of mobile teeth and the formation of a dentition defect accelerate bone tissue resorption. In addition, edentia is not only a serious medical, but also a social and psychological problem. It is especially difficult for patients to experience the removal of the frontal group of teeth - not only is chewing of food impaired, but also the clarity of speech deteriorates and the appearance of the patient changes. Orthopedic treatment carried out in the long term does not always solve a difficult clinical situation. According to the literature, direct prosthetics is of great importance for maintaining optimal anatomical and functional

properties of bone tissue in the area of extracted teeth. The immediate prosthesis covers the surface of the wound from injury during eating and erosion by saliva. The presence of a rigid base helps to bring the edges of the postoperative wound closer together, the formation of a prosthetic bed without bone protrusions and sharp edges of the sockets of extracted teeth. Chewing pressure, which is transmitted through the immediate prosthesis to the edentulous area, helps stimulate the processes of osteogenesis. Direct prosthetics are carried out after tooth extraction and are aimed at accelerating healing and the formation of a prosthetic bed, which creates favorable conditions for subsequent prosthetics. With direct prosthetics, the denture is inserted into the oral cavity immediately after surgery on the surface of the wound (in a time interval from 15 minutes to 24 hours). This helps restore the morphological, functional and aesthetic optimum in the dental system [3, 5]. Meta-studies – improving the effectiveness of periodontal disease treatment. Chronic generalized periodontitis, moderate severity.” The objects of the in-depth study were persons of both sexes aged from 38 to 55 years (average age 45.2 ± 7.4 years). Treatment of periodontal diseases began with careful removal of dental plaque. Local factors contributing to the accumulation of dental plaque have been eliminated. The movable groups of teeth were splinted with the dental material “Polyglass” [5]. The comparison group (Group 1) was formed from 24 individuals who had dentition defects in the frontal region of the lower jaw. Teeth were extracted due to chronic generalized periodontitis in the area of direct traumatic node. Patients in this group refused to manufacture immediate prostheses. All patients had removable orthopedic structures installed in the long term after tooth extraction (from 4 months to one year). periodontal damage in the frontal part of the lower dentition due to functional load in the area of direct traumatic node. These patients required tooth extraction. In all patients, before the teeth were removed,

impressions were taken from both jaws and removable immediate dentures were made. On the day of tooth extraction, removable and mediate dentures were applied to the surface of the jaw wound. The effectiveness of such drugs is determined by the rate at which they are washed out from the wound surface. In this case, it is necessary to maintain the therapeutic properties during the intervals between meals. Therefore, in the second group, this method was used in the process of complex treatment of periodontal diseases. The condition of the periodontal tissues of the teeth, limiting the dentition defect, was assessed, and X-ray studies were carried out. The relative height of the alveolar processes, the degree of their atrophy in this segment compared to other segments, the number of protruding sharp bone edges and exostoses, the degree of elasticity, mobility, pain, as well as the consistency of the mucous tissue were determined by palpation [1, 2]. To assess the mineral density of bone tissue in the area of the extracted teeth, echo-osteometry was performed before the teeth were removed, as well as after 12 months. [4]. The frequency of ultrasonic vibrations emitted by the diagnostic head (DG) of the measuring device is 0.12 ± 0.036 MHz. The device provides measurement of time intervals of ultrasonic waves in the range of 1-300 μ s. The radio pulse is supplied to the transmitting ultrasonic head (UZG-1), with the help of which the probing signal is transmitted through the soft tissue to the bone. After passing through a section of bone, the signal returns to the measuring device. right and left. With USIG-1, it is necessary to install it in the projection of the chin angle of the lower jaw or at the intersection point of the perpendicular lowered from the corner of the mouth to the edge of the body of the lower jaw. A transfer ultrasound is installed on the body of the other half of the lower jaw in the area of the projection of the 3rd–4th teeth. The distances between the receiving sensors (“base”) are measured between their centers. The most frequently repeated time indicators (in Mks) are taken from the digital indicator of the device and listed according to the formula $V=S/T \times 10^4$, where V is the speed of ultrasound propagation (m/s), S is the length of the bone section being studied, T is the travel time Ultrasound (Mks) (sensor readings). Measurements are carried out on both sides and the average value is established. Results of the study and their discussion In patients of the first group, the speed of ultrasound was 2663.5 ± 28.0 m/s ($p < 0.001$). increased by an average

of 29.8 m/s or 1.1%. When studying bone tissue density in patients of the second group, the speed of ultrasound in bone tissue was recorded at 2655.3 ± 24.3 m/s ($p < 0.001$), and after the administration of the treatment complex it increased to 2859.3 ± 9.1 m/s ($p < 0.001$). In patients of the second group, the speed of ultrasound transmission increased by 7.7%, respectively ($p < 0.001$ compared to the baseline). In patients of group 1, the levels of mineral density in the studied areas, despite a long period of rehabilitation (one year), the mineral saturation of the jaw bones in the area of the dentition defect increased slightly. Orthopedic treatment carried out in the long term did not correct the situation. According to X-ray examination, increased bone tissue resorption was observed. Inflammatory phenomena in the remaining periodontal tissues of the teeth were clinically established; in 40% of patients, the fixation of orthopedic structures was unsatisfactory, which led to the use of a repeated course of treatment and correction of orthopedic structures.

Conclusion.

The application of an immediate prosthesis on the surface of the wound promotes not only the formation of the alveolar process, but also the restoration of mineral density in the area of the dentition defect. Clinically, this was manifested by the absence of relapses of chronic generalized periodontitis and high-quality fixation of orthopedic structures.

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